

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CONCEPT "FATHER" IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK LITERARY WORKS

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Annotation: The article deals with comparative analysis of the role of "father" in the families in English and Uzbek fiction. In addition to this role of the concept of father in our culture were noted.

Key words: *parental relations, cultural characteristics, linguo-cultural studies, cultural-national character, paremiological units, parent-child relationship.*

Since the anthropocentric orientation in linguistics has attracted the attention of scholars, many studies have been conducted with culture and language as the main topic. Traditions, which are considered an integral part of any national culture, are, as a rule, expressed in the language. Family traditions are an important part of traditions, which are characteristic of the culture of the British and Uzbek peoples. The results of the research show that parental relations reflected in proverbs are vividly expressed cultural characteristics of English and Uzbek family traditions. In order to reveal the similarities, differences and unique features of some family traditions reflected in English and Uzbek linguo-cultural studies, we turned to speech of these languages. We hope that this will help the reader to understand the use of speech in English and Uzbek languages. The concept of family traditions includes not only holidays, celebrations and rituals, customs, but also traditional relationships passed from generation to generation. A person's relatives, whether they are near or distant, have a certain thing his place

in life. Kinship can be divided into blood relatives and relatives according to the degree of closeness. In this study, we aimed to do a comparative analysis of the relations between this type of relatives in the English and Uzbek languages[1]. Family, families and kinship relations form the culture of the people and show its specific characteristics, and help to realize the national, linguistic image of the world on a large scale. The issue of family relations applies not only to sociology, but also to cultural and linguistic studies. It is natural to approach this problem from the point of view of linguistic and cultural studies. Linguistic units with a cultural-national character attract the attention of researchers with the study of linguistics. Representation of the native speaker's world. Phraseological and paremiological units embodying the national cultural outlook play a cultural role stereotypes.

Family traditions are a considerable part of traditions and they are inherent to the cultures of English and Uzbek nations. The study results show that a parentchild relationship reflected in proverbs vividly express culture-specific features of English and Uzbek family traditions. In order to reveal similarities, differences and unique features of some family traditions reflected in the English and the Uzbek linguoculturology, we have addressed to the proverbs of these languages. This, it is hoped, would assist the reader in comprehending the application of proverbial peculiarities in English and Uzbek. Under the concept of family traditions are not only celebrations, holidays and ceremonies, customs but they also include a traditional relationship passing from one generation into another. A person's relatives no matter whether close or distant they have a certain place in his/her life. Kinship according to its degree of closeness can be divided into blood relatives and inlaws. In this research we aimed to make a comparative analysis of relations among these types of relatives in the English and Uzbek languages. "Family, family bonds and kinship relations form a nation's culture and show its peculiarities and assist to realize widely the national,

linguistic image of the world”. As the issue of family relations touch not only sociological science but also, cultural and linguistic ones, it is natural to approach to this problem from the perspectives of linguoculturology[2].

Approaches to studying a parent-child relationship have been made from different perspectives such as psychiatry and psychology. This issue has attracted the attention of sociologists, psychologists, sociolinguists and linguists for many years. On the basis of literary texts, mass communication publications, poems Lavitskiy describes the concept “Children” of Vitebsk region in Belarus in his scientific article. He investigates children’s life from different prospective of life in which the role and place of parents are inevitable. Go Pintin approaches the issue as a family tradition and compares Chinese and Russian a parent-child relationship basing on the proverbs and sayings of the two languages. Biktagirova carries out comparative analysis of the issue in the concept “Family” on the materials of systematically different languages as English, Turkish and Tatar languages. Adamova investigates the issue in her research dedicated to interpersonal relationships of English and Lak (Northeast Caucasian language) languages. Another research studies the concepts “Mother, father and children” as the representation of the world of “one’s” in the Kuban phraseology. Studying a parent-child relationship in linguoculturology enables to get acquainted with a linguistic image of the world of a certain nation.

The present study is devoted to the comparison of the concept "family" in English and the concept of "family" in Russian, Uzbek analysis of the connotative content of English words and stable phrases that make up the semantic field "family relations". The work investigates the linguistic-cognitive nature of related relationships within the framework of the concept "family". The material of the study was data from a continuous sample of explanatory, synonymous, phraseological and idiomatic dictionaries of English and Uzbek languages, dictionaries and collections of English, Uzbek proverbs. As the object of our

research is the multifaceted concept of "family", its content, the aggregate of English language tools, which serves to designate the lexical and phraseological units that make up the semantic field "family relations", based on the concept of "family", the subject of research are its means representations in Uzbek, Russian and English.

There are many examples of respect for parents. For example, "Listen to your father, who gave you life, do not despise your mother when she is old". That is, it means: "Senga hayot in'om etgan otangni so'zlarini tingla, onang qariganda unga g'amxo'rlik qil". The Uzbek version of the article "See your father, come down the horse" is as follows: "Otangizni ko'rsangiz otdan tushing". This proverb is used figuratively to encourage people to honor their father. Similar proverbs and sayings can be found and analyzed in many languages. The factual paremiological material collected by us is the basis for the division of English and Uzbek folk proverbs into a number of thematic groups. Among them, the thematic group "Father and mother lexeme proverbs" is distinguished by its specific features. The category father and mother lexemes in English and Uzbek proverbs come in a one parema. In some of the paremiological units, the word parents (father and mother) occur as a component of the proverb. We grouped these proverbs into a separate group. In the centuries-old culture and pre-determined moral characteristics of the English people, respect for parents is glorified and disregard for them is strongly condemned. The proverb emphasizes this: Honor the father and the mother.

As a summary it should be highlighted that The following proverbs and sayings reflect the fact that the Uzbek people have a long tradition of honoring, respecting and honoring their parents, namely, to "father". For example, in the stable combination of "Ota rozi - xudo rozi" the level of the father is extremely glorified. In our nation, the fact that children first of all try to get the consent of their fathers is a clear proof of this. Because when you do good to someone or

achieve something, of course, they use the saying, “Otangga rahmat”. It is the dream of every father to hear this applause. After all, in our nation, a child is the face of a parent. The Uzbek “Andisha” is also evident in the article "Ota oldidan o'tma, odob oldidan ketma" in english "Do not go before the father, do not go before the manners." Because there are unwritten rules, such as not speaking back to the father, listening to his advice, not speaking harshly, that are ingrained in our blood[4]. The spiritual image of people is often determined by their attitude towards their parents. These, in turn, are directly linked to religious views.

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